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CONTEMPORARY AZERBAIJANI-GEORGIAN LITERARY RELATIONS: ELIZBAR JAVELIDZE AND ISA HABIBBEYLI

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Abstract

This article explores the contemporary phase of Azerbaijani-Georgian literary relations. These relations have traditionally developed in parallel in both literary and scholarly spheres. The scientific tandem of Leyla Eradze and Dilara Aliyeva, which reached its peak in the 1980s, continued into the independence period. However, these connections have not persisted due to inertia but rather through the creative efforts of individual figures. One may argue that literary relations and environments are shaped and developed by personalities. In this context, the new phase of Azerbaijani-Georgian literary interaction has taken shape around the academic figures Isa Habibbeyli and Elizbar Javelidze. Several of Javelidze's monographs have been published in Azerbaijan within this framework of literary exchange. A substantial part of Isa Habibbeyli's scholarly work has focused on Jalil Mammadguluzadeh, whose literary activity was shaped and developed in the Tbilisi literary environment. As in his research, the Georgian factor has played a significant role in Habibbeyli's overall intellectual work. Georgia appears as a central theme in his studies on Mammadguluzadeh—not only through biographical materials, facts, and documents obtained from Tbilisi's archives, but also in terms of the broader intellectual and cultural context in which the writer operated.

Keywords: Azerbaijani-Georgian, contemporary, literary relations, Javelidze, Habibbeyli.

Azerbaijani-Georgian literary relations have consistently developed in parallel within both literary creativity and the field of scholarship. The academic collaboration between Leyla Eradze and Dilara Aliyeva, which reached its zenith in the 1980s, was sustained into the post-independence period. Yet these connections have not continued by mere inertia; rather, they have relied on the creative output of specific individuals. It can be said that it is personalities who shape and advance literary relations and cultural environments. In the new phase of these relations, the literary milieu between Azerbaijan and Georgia has been shaped significantly through the academic activities of Isa Habibbeyli and Elizbar Javelidze. A large part of Isa Habibbeyli's scholarly work is devoted to the legacy of Jalil Mammadguluzadeh, a prominent Azerbaijani writer whose literary formation and development occurred in the Tbilisi cultural environment.

In contrast, the work of academician Elizbar Javelidze is entirely dedicated to the history and contemporary state of Turkish literature and aesthetic thought. His works have been translated and published in both Russian and Azerbaijani Turkish. In this respect, the intellectual trajectories of these two scholars intersect and complement each other in numerous ways. The election of Isa Habibbeyli as a foreign member of the Georgian Academy of Sciences in 2024 may be regarded as a significant manifestation of his integration into the Georgian scholarly community, the broad and multifaceted nature of his work, and a contemporary example of the friendship and brotherhood between the two nations. Elizbar Javelidze's scholarly activity also maintains a close connection with Azerbaijani literary thought and the works of its prominent representatives. Isa Habibbeyli's collaboration with the Shota Rustaveli Institute of Literature of the Republic of Georgia has facilitated the realization of numerous

academic projects. These collaborations have not been limited to joint efforts but have also ushered in a new stage in the study of reciprocal literary environments.

One of the most significant initiatives of this new phase has been the "Nizami Ganjavi and Shota Rustaveli" project, which culminated in the publication of a monograph under the same title. Projects like this are further advanced through the personal connections among literary figures. The research of academician Elizbar Javelidze—who has dedicated his life to exploring the literary and aesthetic traditions of Turkic thought and which has been published in Baku—has brought new depth and color to these mutual relations.

In his essay titled "*Academician Elizbar Javelidze's Fuzuli-nama*", Isa Habibbeyli describes Javelidze's place in Azerbaijani literature with these words:

"Elizbar Javelidze is Georgia's Masnavi of Molla Rumi. He is the Georgian-language echo of the Kitabi Dede Qorqud. Elizbar Javelidze is the tale of Yunus Emre mingled with the Kura River. He is the reawakened tezkire of Ruhi Baghdad."

Muhammad Fuzuli: Elizbar Javelidze's Devotion to Azerbaijan — The Georgian Scholar's Karbala in Literature, or His Metekhi Fortress in Romantic Thought

Academic Isa Habibbeyli, in these words, sketches a conceptual map of Elizbar Javelidze's scholarly legacy and offers a profound evaluation of his contribution. He describes Javelidze not only as "an old friend of Azerbaijan" but also as "a great ambassador of Oriental studies in the Caucasus." Although Elizbar Javelidze was born in 1938 in Tbilisi, he spent his childhood in Georgia's Bolnisi district, where Azerbaijani communities were densely settled. He received his primary education in the town of Bolnisi and studied at the Faculty of Oriental Studies at Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University from 1956 to 1961, graduating with

distinction. He dedicated his entire career to Oriental studies, rising from the position of junior researcher to that of senior researcher at the G. Tsereteli Institute of Oriental Studies. In 1966, he defended his Candidate of Sciences dissertation on *Ruhî Baghdâdî: Life, Worldview, and Lyricism*, and in 1975, his doctoral dissertation on *Jalal al-Din Rumi: Issues of Worldview*. He served as editor-in-chief of the journals *Criticism and Literaturnaya Gazeta*. In 1988, he became a professor of Turkology at Tbilisi State University and a corresponding member of the Georgian Academy of Sciences. In 1989, by decree of the Supreme Soviet of the Republic of Azerbaijan, he was awarded the honorary title of "Honored Worker of Culture of Azerbaijan." In 1991, he served as Georgia's Minister of Education and Science. In 2013, he was elected a full member of the Georgian National Academy of Sciences. Author of 16 monographs and more than 300 scholarly articles, Javelidze devoted a significant portion of his research to Azerbaijani and Eastern literature. His academic activity is a quintessential example of the bridge built between the two nations. While the foundations of this bridge had already been laid, the Javelidze–Habibbeyli scholarly partnership transformed it into a relationship of true friendship. Professor Bədirxan Əhmədli notes that the literary and academic relations between Georgia and Azerbaijan were gradually fading in the post-independence period. However, Isa Habibbeyli, being well-acquainted with the works of this eminent scholar, took an active interest in their publication and proposed translating some of them into Azerbaijani:

"Isa teacher, knowing the scholarly significance of this distinguished figure whose work was a cornerstone for the long-neglected literary ties, showed interest in publishing his works and proposed the translation and publication of several of them into Azerbaijani." [2] As a result of this renewed collaboration, Javelidze's book *Muhammad Fuzuli: Life, Milieu, and Works* (Baku: Elm və Təhsil, 2017, 144 pp.) was published by the Nizami Ganjavi Institute of Literature, translated by Mirzə Məmmədoğlu and edited by Professor Bədirxan Əhmədli [8]. The relationship with academician Javelidze did not end with the publication of this monograph, further works were also prepared for publication. Even during the Soviet period, Javelidze explored relatively under-researched topics within Turkic literature and made significant contributions by examining these themes from various perspectives. This marked a completely new direction in Georgian philology. It is no coincidence that literary scholar Apollon Silagadze referred to him as the "leader of Georgian Turkology" [7,5], a claim substantiated by Javelidze's own academic work. His monographs *From the Sources of Turkish Literature I: Jalal al-Din Rumi* (1979), *II: Yunus Emre* (1985), and *III: Ashiq Pasha* (2013) stand out for their scholarly rigor and foundational nature. In these works, he also investigated the problem of Sufism, which holds significant importance.

According to A. Silagadze, Javelidze's research represents a novel approach in terms of genre, form, and versification:

"For Elizbar Javelidze, the most cherished theme—if one can put it that way—was Sufism, a philosophical-religious current that once dominated nearly all spheres of life across the Near East and served as the cornerstone of medieval Eastern thought, encompassing culture, aesthetics, ethics, politics, and more." [7,5]

In his monographs, Javelidze examined various aspects and issues of classical divan literature and succeeded in offering a scientific and theoretical analysis of the development of folk and dervish literature. These studies address the intellectual frameworks of medieval religious and aesthetic thought, as well as philosophical dichotomies such as time and space, spirit and body, ultimate reality, the here-and-now versus the hereafter, life and death — all through a rigorous academic lens. Silagadze observes that Javelidze distinguished himself from his contemporaries in this regard. He writes:

"With his analytical approach and conclusions, Javelidze inaugurated a new phase in the study of Sufism. Just one fact suffices: whereas prominent scholars of Sufism such as D. Macdonald, Y. Bertels, M.F. Köprülü, and Z. Gulu-zadeh viewed Sufism as a pantheistic doctrine, Elizbar Javelidze rejected this notion and instead defined pantheism as the foundational principle of Sufism." [7,6] Academic Elizbar Javelidze has inscribed his name in the history of Azerbaijani literature and culture. Most notably, he co-translated the epic *The Book of Dede Korkut* into Georgian alongside Giorgi Shagulashvili. His contribution extended beyond translation, as he devoted considerable attention to this epic in his research. Perhaps it is for this reason that, in his aforementioned essay *To the Fuzuliad of Academician Elizbar Javelidze*, Isa Habibbeyli wrote:

"Elizbar Javelidze is the Georgian Mathnavi of Mawlana Rumi. He is the voice of *The Book of Dede Korkut* in the Georgian language." [3,4]

The life and works of Muhammad Fuzuli, one of the classical figures of Azerbaijani literature, have been the subject of scholarly inquiry for over a century. As a result, little remains unexplored about his biography and literary legacy. His literary heritage has been studied not only in Azerbaijani literary scholarship but also internationally — in Russian, Georgian, Turkish, Kazakh, Uzbek, German, English, and beyond. Therefore, studies conducted outside of Azerbaijan's national scholarly framework have always garnered attention. In this regard, Javelidze's monograph *Muhammad Fuzuli: Life, Milieu, and Works* represents both a valuable contribution to Fuzuli studies and a new chapter in Azerbaijani–Georgian literary relations. The scholarly work "Muhammad Fuzuli: Life, Environment, Creativity" by academician E. Javidli distinguishes itself through its writing style and breadth of research. The author seeks to understand Fuzuli's literary output by also exploring his historical context and environment. The monograph exhibits a degree of formal innovation, combining an academic writing style with interpretive freedom, and offering a conceptual investigation of the poet's life, milieu, and oeuvre within a compact study. It should be noted that even during the Soviet era, E. Javidli adopted this same approach in his research, which afforded him a certain degree of intellectual freedom. It is well understood that when studying the work of any poet or

writer, one must also examine the sociocultural and historical context in which they lived. Javidli does just this: to study the fifteenth and sixteenth-century world of Fuzuli, he consults a range of sources in an effort to determine Baghdad's place and significance in the cultural life of the Muslim world. The researcher emphasizes that during this period, Baghdad was one of the major centers of Eastern thought, home to numerous prominent scholars in the intellectual history of the East. Although Fuzuli himself laments in his poetry the lack of appreciation for verse in his time—evident in lines such as “Our region knows not the worth of verse, / Though beautiful lines bring joy to the soul” and “I live in an era where poetry is despised, / Verses are but unsold wares”—Javidli argues that, in fact, Baghdad paid considerable attention to literature and culture during this time. He writes:

“It is true that in Fuzuli's time, the cultural life of Baghdad no longer matched the richness of its ancient traditions. Nevertheless, even in this period, it surpassed other Eastern cities in various fields of art.”

Javidli asserts that a strong literary school existed in sixteenth-century Baghdad. He supports this claim by referring to sources and listing the contemporaries of Fuzuli—poets who were active in Baghdad's literary circles—as documented by period biographers. These include Faqiri, Sadiq, Ruhi, Kiram, Qilij Bey of Baghdad, Tanha Bey, Mawlana Hush, Kala'i, Zaei, Kalam, Hazan, Mir Qadri, Hasir, Zamir, Ali, and Shamsi Baghdadi. Remarkably, most of these poets composed their works in the Azerbaijani language. Javidli devotes detailed attention to some of them, assessing the influence they may have had on Fuzuli's creative output. One such figure is Ahdi Baghdadi, who is noted not only as a poet but also as a chronicler. This is particularly significant, as Ahdi is the sole biographer who reports that Fuzuli's son, Fazli, also wrote poetry—an insight that has reached us only through his account. Javidli also engages in a discussion about Fuzuli's birth date and place, suggesting, though not definitively concluding, the year 1498. This date was initially proposed by Azerbaijani scholar Hamid Arasli, and Javidli, along with other Orientalists, accepts this view. More broadly, Azerbaijani scholars have played a distinctive role in Fuzuli studies, and like many researchers, Javidli does not always agree with all prevailing views. The academician also explores the origins of Fuzuli's pen name. Relying on the poet's own writings, he recounts that Muhammad, as he rode the “bay steed through the galaxy of poetry,” sought a pen name befitting his poetic persona and eventually chose “Fuzuli.” In recounting the poet's life, Javidli refers to Fuzuli's qasidas (odes), using them to illuminate certain aspects of his personal history. For instance, based on the line in a qasida dedicated to a judge of Baghdad—“You have ruled on my punishment, and surely there is no need for reconsideration”—Javidli concludes that Fuzuli may have lost his position during the Safavid reign. At any rate, he seems to have been unemployed and in dire straits under Ottoman rule in Baghdad. The poet sought the favor of Ottoman dignitaries by composing elegant qasidas that allude to his financial struggles and difficult life.

Javidli grounds this interpretation in the qasidas Fuzuli addressed to Grand Vizier Ibrahim Pasha, Nişancı Pasha Celal Çelebi, Ayaz Pasha, Qaziasker Qazi Çelebi, Üveys Pasha, and other Ottoman officials. Despite his efforts, however, the poet received little attention from the Ottoman sultans, and gestures of generosity toward him were rare. One such instance was Sultan Suleiman the Magnificent's response to Fuzuli's qasida by granting him a stipend of nine akchas. According to Javidli, after much hardship, the poet was finally granted his request, and the imperial decree awarding the stipend brought him immense joy. However, as Fuzuli's satirical and ironic work “Complaint” (“Şikayətnamə”) reveals, this joy was short-lived, as the poet was subjected to bureaucratic harassment by local officials. Javidli also analyzes Fuzuli's ghazals, highlighting him as a master of the form and a poet of love. The scholar devotes special attention to Fuzuli's “Layla and Majnun” and consults Arabic sources to examine the evolution of this love legend in various narratives. For example, he recounts an Arab version in which a young man, hearing of Layla's beauty, becomes determined to see her. He begins visiting the household of Lady Karima, whom Layla and her companions frequently visit. One day, Layla and Qays meet. In celebration, Qays slaughters a she-camel to feast the women, and the festivities continue for several days. E. Javidli's study *The Aesthetics of Turkish Folklore* is also notable for its functionality, scope, and stylistic features. For the first time, the author attempts to investigate the ethical and aesthetic dimensions of medieval Near Eastern Islam and Turkish folklore. He seeks to present a general view of the moral-aesthetic worldview of ancient Eastern civilizations and the medieval Near East. He analyzes the phenomenon of laughter in the works of Molla Nasreddin and in the classical Turkish epic traditions such as *Dede Qorqud* and *Koroghlu*, and explores the symbolic-aesthetic significance of inscriptions on ritual stones.

What is new in this work is the researcher's aesthetic lens: he studies the mutual aesthetic relationship between subject and object and searches for modernity in antiquity. As he notes:

“As art specialists suggest, these hunting scenes, as seen through the eyes of the hunter, are neither mindless imitations nor primitive depictions. Rather, they follow a certain design, restraint, and artistic logic.” [6,48]

Thus, depictions in folklore carry great meaning, and each one has significance. Laughter is not merely an expression of joy or happiness but a manifestation of human artistic thought in various forms. Human nature is complex and changeable, reflecting individual character. Javidli seeks to reveal the nature of laughter in Molla Nasreddin's anecdotes, tracing their internal logic—and succeeds in doing so. Referring to philosophical perspectives from Plato, Aristotle, and others on laughter, he outlines the particular character of humor in Molla Nasreddin's works, also citing Azerbaijani and Turkish scholars.

In one of his assertions, he convincingly states:

“It is now difficult to determine precisely when laughter in Turkish folklore acquired its powerful force.

However, in my opinion, this must have occurred in the 13th century, when the ancestors of the Ottoman Turks—a branch of the Oghuz—retreated from the Mongols, passed through northern Iran and Azerbaijan into Anatolia, and entered the military service of the Seljuk sultanate, ultimately binding their fate to it and merging with Seljuk society.” [1]

As previously mentioned, academician Elizbar Javelidze also translated the epic *Kitabi Dede Gorgud* into Georgian. It appears that this translation led him into deeper explorations and inspired scholarly research on the epic itself. It is well known that this epic has been studied from various perspectives in Azerbaijan and across the Turkic world. However, E. Javelidze approached *Kitabi Dede Gorgud* from the standpoint of artistic and aesthetic categories, investigating the customs, traditions, and moral codes embedded within. In other words, what kind of spiritual values and wisdom do Dede Gorgud and the characters within the epic represent? What does this epic tell us about the invincibility of the Turks and the indomitability of their military might?

The scholar arrives at the following conclusion:

“...It is significant and noteworthy that Gorgud himself initiates both speech and song, for in doing so, he narrates the foundational structure of the lifestyle and traditions of all Oghuz peoples. The worldview shaped around heroism and bravery, the folk wisdom and ethical faith of this tribe, are conveyed with such conciseness and simplicity that it is nearly impossible for either reader or listener not to be struck with awe.” [1]

By examining the characters of Dede Gorgud, the researcher simultaneously explores human nature and character in general, thereby gaining insight into the character and essence of the Oghuz people of that era.

In the scholarly work of academician Isa Habibbayli, Tbilisi and its literary milieu occupy a distinct and prominent place. This is largely due to the fact that a significant portion of his research is devoted to the creative legacy of Jalil Mammadguluzadeh. Mammadguluzadeh graduated from the Gori Pedagogical Seminary and spent a considerable part of his life in Tbilisi, actively participating in its literary scene. His activities at the *Sharqi-Rus* newspaper, the publication of his first short story "The Mailbox," the establishment of the *Geyrat* printing house together with Omar Faig Nemanzadeh, and ultimately the founding of the first satirical press organ in the East, *Molla Nasreddin*, all firmly embedded him within the Tbilisi literary environment—not just as a participant but as an integral part of it.

In the course of researching Mammadguluzadeh's life and work, academician Isa Habibbayli conducted studies in Georgia, uncovering numerous archival materials related to both the activities of the Gori Seminary and Mammadguluzadeh's life and creative development within the Tbilisi literary context. His articles such as "The Gori Seminary and the Intellectuals of Nakhchivan," "Chernyshevsky and the Intellectuals of Nakhchivan," "Pushkin Days at the Gori Seminary," and "A Scholarly Chronicle of Our Educational His-

tory" introduced new perspectives on the Gori Seminary and the Georgian educational environment. Isa Habibbayli has made significant contributions to unearthing documents and facts from the archives of Gori and Tbilisi that pertain to the history of Azerbaijani education and culture.

For example, his research revealed that Mammad agha Shahtakhtli served as editor of the *Kaspi* newspaper from June 1891. [4, p. 146] In his studies on Shahtakhtli's editorship of *Sharqi-Rus*, the researcher not only uncovers new documents and facts but also arrives at informed scholarly conclusions. Regarding the Tbilisi period of Shahtakhtli's life and work, he writes:

“In 1902, Muhammad agha Shahtakhtli returned to Tbilisi for the fourth time in his life. This return was deliberate and aimed at purposeful, practical activity.” [4, p. 149]

From these studies, we also learn that Shahtakhtli sold his share of his ancestral estate in the village of Shahtakht for eighteen thousand manats to finance the establishment of a printing house in Tbilisi. Through detailed research, it becomes evident that the writer

“...purchased the printing machinery from a German company via their Moscow-based agent, Miller, and had them transported to Tbilisi. He then commissioned the typesets and letter cases at the German 'Mader' foundry located on Sadovaya Street in Tbilisi.” [4, p. 151]

Such detailed accounts are made possible only through archival documents and factual sources.

Georgia is a recurring theme in Isa Habibbayli's research on Jalil Mammadguluzadeh. This relevance is not limited to the biographical materials and archival documents obtained from Tbilisi but also encompasses Mammadguluzadeh's intellectual engagement with that environment. Every aspect of the writer's creative output—its themes, character analyses, and ideological foundations—gains greater clarity when contextualized within his life experiences, including those in Georgia.

Of particular significance are the new archival materials Isa Habibbayli uncovered regarding Mammadguluzadeh's student years at the Gori Seminary, bringing to light previously unexplored aspects of his biography. These findings reveal that he studied under distinguished pedagogues such as A.O. Chernyaevsky, D.D. Semyonov, N.N. Novospassky, N.O. Lomouri, and Azerbaijani instructors like Mirza Abdusalam Akhundzadeh and Safarali bey Valibeyov, whose educational, literary, and pedagogical views left a lasting impression on him. [5, p. 131]

It also becomes clear that young Jalil actively participated in cultural and public events at the seminary and demonstrated his abilities in composition and translation classes. Based on archival materials, the researcher concludes:

“The report of Jalil Mammadguluzadeh's trial lesson, prepared on September 29, 1886, while undergoing pedagogical training at the elementary school attached to the Gori Seminary, clearly demonstrates his mastery of written expression and his formation as a young pedagogue versed in the most modern educational principles.” [5, p. 131]

Only through the language of documents and the strength of facts can such conclusions be drawn—and this is precisely what the researcher has accomplished. He obtained the report of Mammadguluzadeh's trial lesson from the Georgian Museum of Public Education. By studying the decrees of the Caucasus Educational District from that period, the researcher also discovered that Mammadguluzadeh's academic performance declined following the dismissal of Director D.D. Semyonov, a progressive democrat, due to an increase in prohibitions and the imposition of a stricter regime at the seminary. The reprimand he received for returning late to the dormitory after a concert on January 16, 1887, was in fact a pretext; in reality, Mammadguluzadeh underwent a significant process of intellectual development at the Gori Seminary that influenced his later literary output.

Academician Isa Habibbayli's book *Jalil Mammadguluzadeh: His Milieu and Contemporaries* (Baku, Azerneshr, 1997) is of great importance for its wealth of factual and documentary evidence. A large portion of these materials were obtained from Georgian archives and were introduced into Azerbaijani literary scholarship for the first time.

As in his scholarly work, the Georgia factor has also played a central role in Isa Habibbayli's professional life. The research conducted by academician E. Javelidze on Turkish and Azerbaijani literature during the Soviet era remained largely unreciprocated. Yet, Isa Habibbayli has continued the legacy of the Samed Vurghun–Giorgi Leonidze friendship in the realm of scholarship through the academic collaboration between Leyla Eradze and Dilara Aliyeva. As B. Ahmadli writes:

“...the literary connections once symbolized by Dilara Aliyeva and Leya Eradze were later nearly forgotten or not maintained at the previous level. However, there are ample political, economic, literary, and cultural factors binding the Azerbaijani and Georgian peoples together. Advancing this connection falls upon the shoulders of the new generation of intellectuals. It

seems that this is why academician Isa Habibbayli considered it necessary to lay the foundation for renewing this friendship.” [2]

The scholarly tandem of academician Isa Habibbayli and academician Elizbar Javelidze has become a crucial element in the further development of Azerbaijani and Georgian literary studies. For this reason, academician Elizbar Javelidze was awarded the honorary title of “Honored Cultural Worker of Azerbaijan” by the decree of the Supreme Soviet of the Azerbaijan Republic in 1989, and academician Isa Habibbayli was elected a foreign member of the Georgian National Academy of Sciences by its resolution dated July 10, 2024. These honors represent a high recognition by the Azerbaijani state of Georgian scholarship, and likewise, a sincere appreciation by Georgia of Azerbaijani science.

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